

PAPER NUMBER: 1853

Composites Manufacturing and Processing - Session 2

**PREDICTION OF PROCESS-INDUCED DEFORMATIONS USING DEEP
LEARNING INTERFACED FINITE ELEMENT CONSTITUTIVE
MODELS**

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Problem Description:

Process induced deformation in thermoset parts

Example of process induced deformations in L-shaped part (cross-ply)

Process induced defects arises due to:

- Thermal expansion
- Chemical shrinkage
- Lay-up configuration, mold material, composite part thickness etc.,

The cure state variables are

- The degree of cure, X
- The glass transition temperature, T_g

Non-parametric cure model:

Characterization tests at rates of 1.5°C/min, 0.55°C/min, and 0.5°C/min & with isothermal dwells at 180°C, 175°C, and 185°C, respectively + some with partial curing

Diffusion Cure Kinetics (CK) Model (Cole, et al. [2005]) and DiBenedetto's model (Stutz, et al. [1990])

$$\left(\frac{dX}{dt}, T_g\right) = f(X, T)$$

Drawbacks:

- No dependency on process condition variables.
- The part often follows different temperature profile.
- CK model parameters treated deterministically.

Non-parametric neural network model

$$\left(\frac{dX}{dt}, T_g\right) = f(X, T, r)$$

Case study: Curing of Z-shaped part ($[\pm 45^\circ/0-90^\circ]_{4s}$) made of 15 plies on Invar mold

Residual stress in X direction upon demoulding (deformation scaling factor = 5)

Residual stress field prediction based on visco-elastic constitutive model (Svanberg, et al. [2004])

- Validation of the internal residual stress field is achieved through a comparison of process induced deformations (PIDs).

Summary and Conclusions:

- The non-parametric model makes accurate state transitions predictions considering the influence of process conditions.
- The proposed model when interfaced with the constitutive model predicts the PIDs that correlates more closely with experimental laser scan measures for the case of Z-shape thermoset part.

Outlooks:

- The model is implemented to conduct stochastic curing simulations, allowing for the quantification of uncertainties associated with cure temperature cycles.
- Characterization of complex resin formulations for newer thermoset materials.